

***Exploring (Dis)Continuities of Homosexuality and Religion in Nigerian Literary Discourse:
A Study of Chinelo Okparanta's Under the Udala Trees and Chris Abani's Graceland.***

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Abstract:

This paper aims at examining the representation and exploration of homosexuality within the context of religion in Nigerian literary space. Nigeria, a country marked by its rich literary tradition and diverse religious landscape, grapples with the intersection of traditional religious beliefs and modern understandings of human sexuality. Prominent in the Nigerian religious space are Christianity, Islam and the Traditional worship. Definitely, the religious beliefs of the people actually map our 'Africaness' and African identity. Data gathering and analysis are carried out in Chinelo Okparanta's Under the Udala Trees and Chris Abani's Graceland as our methodology employed to examine this topic. The authors navigate the intricacies of religion and sexuality, shedding light on the challenges faced by individuals within religious communities and broader society. There is paucity of researches on homosexuality being explored from the lens of religion. Certainly, beliefs must teach morality, the gap this paper intends to fill. It considers how authors challenge prevailing norms, advocating for greater empathy, inclusivity, and understanding of diverse sexual orientations within religious and cultural contexts. The theories of masculinity, radical feminism and modernism are engaged. The paper concludes by stating the crucial yet ambivalent public role of religion in matters of sexuality, social justice and human rights in contemporary Africa.

Keywords: Homosexuality, Religion, (Dis)Continuity, Gender, Morality, Same-sex Marriage, Deprivation, Belief.

Introduction

It is established that literature is a platform for dialogue, reflection, resolution and social critique. It invites readers to engage critically with several issues among which are of religious faith, sexuality, and cultural identity that map our contemporary Nigerian or African society. The paper examines how morality can be maintained in our contemporary society where the young minds are on the vanguard of exploring new religious and personal beliefs among which is homosexuality. Drawing on a selection of Nigerian literary works spanning different genres and periods, this study analyzes the sensitive portrayal of homosexuality and its relationship with religious orthodoxy, geography, socio cultural changes, social stigma, and personal identity. Chinelo Okparanta's *Under the Udala Trees*; and Chris Abani's *Graceland* are the primary literary texts. The authors examine the portrayal of characters who confront the tension between their sexual orientation, the motive behind their decisions and religious beliefs, as well as the social stigma and discrimination they encounter in their quest for self-acceptance and authenticity.

Our research discovers the scholarship gap that many scholars and religious academic journals, somehow, do not give adequate attention to this issue of “inter-marriage” between religion and sexuality. Supporting this claim is the submission of Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:21), stating that “against the emerging understanding of homosexuality as an issue of human rights and public health, it is rather surprising that the subject so far has received very little attention in the circles of either African theology or the study of religion in Africa. Just as an illustration, the *Journal of Religion in Africa*, a leading journal in the field of African religious studies, until 2013 had never published an article explicitly focusing on issues of homosexuality.” The study of religion in Africa, according to Chitando (2008, 121), is characterised by a ‘utilitarian approach’, meaning that it examines both the negative and constructive roles of religion in a variety of socio-political issues and practical concerns, but so far this has not resulted in a systematic engagement with homophobia and same sex sexuality. On the contrary, it seems that scholars until recently shied away from addressing these controversial issues. Against this background, we hope that this research paper is a timely intervention adequately addressing this gap in existing research.

According to Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:2), it is established that:

The issues of same-sex relationships and gay and lesbian rights are the subject of public and political controversy in many African societies today. Frequently, these controversies receive widespread attention both locally and globally, such as with the Anti-Homosexuality Bill in Uganda. In the international media, these cases tend to be presented as revealing a deeply-rooted homophobia in Africa fuelled by religious and cultural traditions. But so far little energy is expended in understanding these controversies in all their complexity and the critical role religion plays in them.

We should bear it in mind the Nigeria's Same Sex Marriage (Prohibition) Act of 2014 which reflects the country's conservative stance on homosexuality, deeply rooted in cultural and religious traditions. This Prohibition Act was used to facilitate the understanding of the different stages in the formation and practice of homosexuality in Nigeria. The Act also facilitated the understanding of how and why homosexuality spreads all over Nigeria to the extent of homosexuals protesting publicly for their rights. (Chinedu-Okeke and Ijeoma Obi (2021:46). Mkhize and Mthembu (Citation 2023, p. 381), as quoted by Ayo Osinanwo and Mathew Alugbin (2024), posit that ‘several sub-Saharan African countries, including Nigeria, Uganda, South Sudan, and Mauritania, legislated against queer identities and same-sex sexual activities to silence the voices and experiences of those engaging in them.’ Nigeria as a nation views religion and sexuality from different perspectives and polarities.

According to Chinelo Okparanta (2015: 280), she submits that “according to a 2012 Win-Gallup International Global Index of Religiosity and Atheism, Nigeria ranks as the second-most-religious country surveyed, following very closely behind Ghana.” Under the geographical distribution, different regions of Nigeria have predominant religious affiliations. In the northern states, Islam is the dominant religion, while Christianity is more prevalent in the southern and middle belt regions. This geographical distribution often shapes the religious landscape of the country, with mosques and Islamic cultural practices more visible in the north, and churches and Christian customs more prevalent in the south. Ethnic groups in Nigeria often have strong ties to particular religions. For example, the Hausa-Fulani ethnic group in the north is predominantly Muslim, while the Yoruba and Igbo ethnic groups in the south are mainly Christian. This linkage between ethnicity and

religion can influence social identities and dynamics within communities. In the same vein, religious affiliations sometimes intersect with political power in Nigeria. Political leaders may align themselves with particular religious' groups to gain support or legitimacy, leading to tensions or conflicts between religious communities. Additionally, political decisions and policies may be influenced by religious considerations, particularly in areas where one religion holds significant sway.

While religion can foster social cohesion within communities, it can also be a source of conflict. Interreligious tensions and violence have occurred in Nigeria, often fueled by competition for resources, political power, or ideological differences. Instances of religious extremism and terrorism have further complicated the relationship between religion, territory, and identity. Religion influences various aspects of cultural expression in Nigeria, including music, art, literature, and rituals. Different religious communities have their unique cultural practices and traditions, contributing to the rich tapestry of Nigerian society. Despite challenges, there are also instances of interfaith dialogue and cooperation in Nigeria. Efforts by religious and community leaders to promote understanding, tolerance, and peaceful coexistence have been instrumental in mitigating conflicts and fostering harmony among diverse religious groups.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of the study is to analyse, in the selected literary texts, the representation and exploration of homosexuality within the context of religion in Nigerian literary space with the aim of achieving the following objectives:

1. to examine the concept of homosexuality as it relates to individuals for gender recognition and equality,
2. to navigate the intricacies of religion and sexuality and the challenges faced by individuals within religious communities, and
3. to challenge prevailing norms, advocating for greater empathy, inclusivity, and understanding of diverse sexual orientations within religious and cultural contexts.

Research Questions

The following research questions form the bases on which this research is carried out as tools guiding our analysis, findings, and conclusion.

- 1) What is the place of homosexuality in African culture, content and context?
- 2) Is homosexuality antithetical to religion despite its establishment in religious books?
- 3) What are the roles of religion in matters of sexuality, social justice and human rights in contemporary African society?
- 4) What is the relationship between religion, homosexuality, gender equality and fundamental human rights?

Literature Review

The exploration of the review of literary works for this paper is done through the discussions on the topics and textual analysis discussed below.

The Intersection of Religion and Homosexuality

The homosexuality debate is a controversial issue that has attracted the concern of various countries all over the world. As a sexual orientation, homosexuality is "an enduring pattern of emotional, romantic, and/or sexual attractions to people of the same sex. In the last decade, several Western countries have greatly enhanced the rights of sexual minorities in their societies. Same-sex relationship/marriage is now legal in most states in the United States, while about twenty-three countries in Europe presently allow same-sex marriage or some form of civil partnership. However, Africa on the other hand is witnessing a rise in the number of countries further criminalizing sexual minorities and homophobia is rising across the continent. Thus, 38 countries out of 76 countries in the world that sees homosexuality as illegal are in Africa and in 4 out of these 38 countries, homosexuality is punishable by death including Nigeria. (Chinonye Faith Chinedu-Okeke and Ijeoma Obi, 2021:1) Religion is a complex and multifaceted concept that encompasses a set of beliefs, practices, and rituals centered around a higher power, divine being, or spiritual entity. It often involves: 1. Faith and worship: Belief in and reverence for a deity or deities. 2. Moral codes and ethics: Guidelines for behavior and decision-making. 3. Rituals and practices: Ceremonies, prayers, and other observances. 4. Community and tradition: Shared beliefs and practices within a community. Religion is expected to provide: 1. Meaning and purpose: A sense of direction and significance. 2. Comfort and solace: Support during difficult times. 3. Guidance and wisdom: Moral and ethical framework. 4. Community and belonging: Connection with others.

But rather, religion today produces conflict and all forms of hypocrisy. "Within religious communities in Nigeria, LGBTQ individuals often find themselves navigating complex internal conflicts as they strive to reconcile their faith with their sexual or gender identity. Many grapple with feelings of alienation and rejection from their religious institutions and communities, exacerbating their sense of isolation." (Ayo Osinanwo and Mathew Alugbin, 2024) Religious teachings and beliefs wield substantial influence in shaping attitudes towards LGBTQ+ communities (Beagan & Hattie, 2015). With a population of over 220 million people, where approximately 100 million (45%) identify with Islamic religion, while approximately 93 million (42%) identify with Christianity, Nigeria has been described as home to some of the world's largest Christian and Muslim populations (Diamant, 2019). Both Christianity and Islam, the two dominant religions in the country, denounce homosexuality as sinful and contrary to divine law. Religious leaders frequently reinforce negative stereotypes about LGBTQ individuals, depicting homosexuality as a moral transgression and advocating for punitive measures against those who identify as LGBTQ.

To provide a more in-depth understanding of the nexus between religion and the politicisation of homosexuality in Africa, we propose a focus on the notion of 'public religion'. This enables an analysis of the conflation of religion with politics and public life that is characteristic of the configuration of religion – specifically the major religions, Christianity and Islam – in contemporary African societies and that is clearly reflected in the debates about homosexuality. The notion of 'public religion' is derived from sociologist José Casanova who, in his 1994 book

Public Religions in the Modern World, develops the thesis of the deprivatisation of religion in the modern world and its renewed manifestation in the public sphere:

By deprivatization I mean the fact that religious traditions throughout the world are refusing to accept the marginal and privatized role which theories of modernity as well as theories of secularization had reserved for them. Social movements have appeared which either are religious in nature or are challenging in the name of religion the legitimacy and autonomy of the primary secular spheres, the state and the market economy. Similarly, religious institutions and organizations refuse to restrict themselves to the pastoral care of individual souls and continue to raise questions about the interconnections of private and public morality and to challenge the claims of the subsystems, particularly states and markets, to be exempt from extraneous normative considerations. (Casanova 1994, 5)

As Casanova has acknowledged himself, his thesis about the deprivatisation of religion is rather Western-centric (Casanova 2008). The abundance of scholarship on religion in Africa makes it clear that in Africa (as in many other parts of the world) religion has never been a private affair and has always conflated with politics and public life (Ellis and Ter Haar 2007). African are fully committed to religion. They openly confess their beliefs without fear or favour. Any movement or policy, not to talk of new innovations that might want to challenge those beliefs are vehemently opposed to in some African states while some are trying to partially accept the norms in order for them not to be tagged racist nations who deprive their citizens their fundamental human rights. For instance, South Africa is such a nation which strives to accept the union between religion and (homo)sexuality. According to Marion Burchardt (2013: 239) in analysing South Africa says that, 'the concomitant rise of the public presence of sexual minorities' politics and of "public religion" is often fashioned antagonistically'. Marion Burchardt (2013: 239) posits further that in South Africa, and other parts of Africa:

The resistance against the progressive institutionalization of equality before the law of same-sex partnerships can even be viewed as a key motif of the emergence of particular kinds of public religion. In other words, both religious and sexual rights mobilizations may depend on and thrive in reaction to one another, sometimes entering a symbiotic social existence.

As stated earlier, we must understand that South Africa stands out among other African nations about its progressive constitutional protection against discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation, and its legalisation of same-sex civil unions. Though this, in any measure, has not led to widespread social acceptance of same-sex relationships. Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:19) declare that in other parts of the continent same-sex sexualities and identities have also become more visible, not at least as a result of global discourses and politics; they have become central public concerns and evoked particular public religious responses.

The ongoing atmosphere in African continent on religion and sexual identity calls for a proactive measure that will capture the situation in many African countries where religion is mobilised for a singular purpose to circumvent same-sex communities and LGBTI identities from becoming socially visible and to prevent sexual minority rights from being recognised. This situation can

most clearly be illustrated with what has been called ‘anticipatory legislation’: ‘In many African countries, (same-sex) marriage and adoption of children (by people in same-sex relationships) are, of course, not issues that gays there are concerned about, yet bills or laws are passed in anticipation’ (Kaoma 2013:85).

We understand that Nigeria’s Same Sex Marriage Prohibition Act, 2014, as discussed in Oguntola Laguda and van Klinken’s contribution, is a good case in point because the act was assumedly put in place, in some perceptions, basically to protect some personal religious beliefs. It is the legalisation of same-sex marriage in other parts of the world that inspired Nigerian legislators to propose and pass a Bill preventing similar developments to happen in their country, even if there is no sign that local same-sex communities think about campaigning for equal marriage rights since they are concerned about much more basic issues. In other words, more than a strong, visible and active local same-sex or LGBTI community, in many cases it is international developments and foreign factors, and their possible empowering effects on local communities, that give rise to religious, as well as political and judicial, mobilisations against same-sex sexuality in Africa. Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:20).

In Egypt, as another case study, even though Islamic law is not applied and the country has no law against homosexuality, homosexuals are increasingly prosecuted – a development that coincides with the recent growth in the number of fatwa-s on homosexuality and articles about homosexuality published in Egyptian Islamic media, as well as coeval Egyptian judicial verdicts. Interestingly, Egypt, a country not seldom considered as Middle Eastern, in some quarters, rather than African, is affected by similar dynamics as other countries on the continent, both with regard to the public significance of religion and the politicisation of homosexuality. Apart from Egypt, there are continue unravelling the intersections of religion and politics in the politicisation of homosexuality in various African countries. In Zimbabwe, President Mugabe already since the mid-1990s opposes homosexuality and LGBTI rights with much fervour, engaging in popular religious rhetoric and with enthusiastic support from religious leaders. Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:23).

Likewise, in Kenya, out of their sense of being marginalised in Kenyan, largely Christian-dominated politics, and as part of their struggle for the preservation of presumed Islamic and/or African identity against ‘Western (Christian) culture’, have mobilised against homosexuality, thereby ironically disregarding the traditions of same-sex sexuality in coastal Muslim communities. Joseph Hellweg (2016) presents a case study of the politicisation of homosexuality in a francophone context, Côte d’Ivoire (Ivory Coast). Different from Britain, France did not impose anti-homosexual laws in its colonies, and different from fellow former French colony Cameroon, Côte d’Ivoire has not adopted such a law after independence. In fact, the country has been relatively tolerant towards LGBTI people. Yet recent years have witnessed an increase in religious and political homophobia as well as an emergence of state-sponsored anti-gay violence. Hellweg (2016) explains this with reference to the country’s recent history, arguing that in the aftermath of a long political crisis, grounded in debates over national identity phrased in idioms of religion and ethnicity, a new definition of autochthony emerged, based on sexuality. In particular, Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:24), submit that the legalisation of same-sex marriage in France allowed religious and political leaders in Côte d’Ivoire to affirm national sovereignty over and against neo-colonial influence, negotiating the country’s place in the broader political economy of global neo-liberalism.

Adriaan van Klinken and Ezra Chitando (2016:25-26) establish that in Liberia, their focus is on the New Citizens Movement, a group formed in 2012 by both Christian and Muslim leaders to guide Liberia's moral development which soon initiated an anti-gay rights campaign. Drawing attention to grassroots collective action by local anti-LGBTI activists who genuinely believe that they are defending the nation's welfare. Currier and Cruz, as quoted in Klinken et al (2016:26), not only highlight the local-rootedness of mobilisations against homosexuality in Liberia, but also raise the question how such a mobilisation might serve to temporarily quell or assuage interreligious tensions in the country. A similar concern with the nation's welfare, in particular a concern with HIV prevention, is reflected in the mobilisation against homosexuality in Senegal.

Here, Christophe Broqua (2016) points out how in Senegal homosexuals, or the group of men having sex with other men, were initially included in the country's national AIDS control plan. This changed dramatically in the late 1990s and early 2000s when Jamra, an Islamic organisation that itself is involved in AIDS control, started to mobilise against homosexuality, successfully constructing it as a public problem and as a threat to the 'religious morality' that should prevent the spread of HIV. As a result, homosexuality became deeply politicised, hindering not only attempts to decriminalise same-sex practices but also prevention campaigns targeting on vulnerable groups including men having sex with other men. Continuity of campaigns on the relationship between religion and homosexuality continue to receive focus on local mobilisations by Christian and Islamic bodies.

The brief overview of this issue as seen in some African nations gives us clear understanding on how homosexuality is handled by the political and religious organizations which is deeply rooted in politics of all shades.

One field in which religious homophobia has begun to be addressed is African literature, as Pauline Mateveke (2016) shows in her paper in *Public Religion and the Politics of Homosexuality in Africa*, with reference to recent Zimbabwean literary writing. Taking up Achebe's notions of the writer as a public critic and of literature as a means to social reform, Mateveke explores how two literary texts – one fiction, the other (auto)biography – have 'dared' to tell the story of homosexuality in the Zimbabwean context. These writers thereby interrogate the patterns of silencing and stigmatising homosexuality in society, question the antagonistic narrative of Christianity and homosexuality, and foreground the potential in indigenous religions to appreciate same-sex sexuality. Upon this submission do we now examine the portrayal of homosexuality and religion in the two selected literary texts

The Portrayal of Homosexuality and Religion in Chinelo Okparanta's *Under the Udala Trees*; and Chris Abani's *Graceland*

Literature is one of the voices of the voiceless. The two selected authors have tried to navigate between religiosity and homosexuality, the blending of the two opposing sides. *Under the Udala Trees* presents a story of a young lady who struggles with her strong feelings of love for others of her gender, though raised in a religious home. She falls in love with her roommate, Amina, and their relationship is solid and sincere because she declares that "Someone kissed me once before. My best friend from Ojoto. It didn't feel the way it feels with you." ... After some time she asked, "How exactly does it feel with me?" ... Eventually I simply said, "Tingly and good and like everything is perfect in the world." P.106. But the society and religion will not allow it to thrive. The author opens the narrative with the conversation between Ijeoma and her mother which bothers on religion. Ijeoma says:

That first session, Mama opened the pages of her Bible. Page one, chapter one, verse one. She began: *I In the beginning God created the heavens and the earth...* Her voice was gentle and calm. There was a steady cadence to it as she went down the page and then back up to chapter two. I followed along with my own Bible, Papa's old one, as we made our way through. P. 2

The mother drums it into her ear daily that God created "*Nwoke na nwunye. Adam na Eve. Man and wife.*" P. 12. She constantly reasons with the mother about her religious stands. The mother believes that biblical Lot was a good man, Ijeoma thinks otherwise because he was willing to give his daughters to be sexually molested in place of his guests. The reference to the biblical Lot here shows the relationship that exist between religion and (homo)sexuality. It equally ascertains that homosexuality has been from the beginning of the creation of the world. It is not a new innovation by the new generation of young minds.

"Lot was a good man," Mama said.

"Hospitable. Was willing to protect his guests from sin."

"But he offered up his own daughters to be done with as the Sodomites wished," I replied.

"How did that make him a good man?" ...

"It isn't," Mama said. "Everybody knows what lesson we should take from that story. Man must not lie with man, and if man does, man will be destroyed. Which is why God destroyed Sodom and Gomorrah." "It couldn't have been because they were selfish and inhospitable and violent?" I asked. "It has to be that other thing?" ...

Pg. 16

The commendation by Mama about the hospitality of Lot reveals the hypocritical nature of leaders. Mama is the leader here who occupies the positions of both the spiritual and maternal head to Ijeoma, the representative of the youths of nowadays. Lot was willing to 'protect his guests from sin', yet, he was ready to surrender his daughters to be sexually abused by the protesters. A hospitality indeed! The source, perpetrators, and leadership perceptions of homosexuality are uncovered here by the Bible.

Mama is quick to defend her stand that homosexuality is evil because it does not allow for procreation which was God's original design for humans. Once that is against the original plan, then it must be condemned because it is an 'abomination'. Mama says:

"Besides, how can people be fruitful and multiply if they carry on in that way? ... the fact that it does not allow for procreation."

Ijeoma is equally quick to reason it out that:

I knew enough to know that the grammar school teacher and his wife could not have children. ... "But even with a man and a woman, procreation is not always possible. Is that an abomination too?" I asked. "What if there's nothing they can do about it?" "God intended for it to be man and woman. And God intended also for man and woman to bear children. It is the way it should be, so yes, it is an abomination if it is not man and woman. And it is an abomination if man and woman cannot bear a child." P 69.

The author tries to establish that procreation should not be the only major yardstick for marriage between a man and a woman as erroneously believed. Love and mutual understanding should. The love relationship between Ijeoma and Amina begins while both of them live in the same room under the care of the Teacher, ijeoma's uncle.

Back in the hovel, our towels fell to the floor. In the near darkness, our hands moved across our bodies. We took in with our fingers the curves of our flesh, the grooves. Our hands, rather than our voices, seemed to do the speaking. Our breaths mingled with the night sounds. Eventually our lips met. This was the beginning; our bodies being touched by the fire that was in each other's flesh. P 105.

Amina and Ijeoma continue their relationship, though in secret, based on their love for each other. The idea of making their relationship open to the society occurs to them but they are well aware enough to know that the society will oppose such relationship that is expected to snowball into marriage. That is why Amina declares to Ijeoma:

"WE MIGHT AS well be married," Amina said one day. A moment passed and a thought occurred to me. I asked, "You mean to each other? Or do you mean to other people?" She rolled her eyes at me. "Of course I mean to each other. I mean that it would be nice to be married to you." "It would be nice to be married to you too," I said. P 106.

Marriage is the agreement between two people to live together. Amina and Ijeoma agree together to marry, but the society and human reasoning will not allow that. Marriage is based on love but many marriages today are based on religious and cultural beliefs void of love. Whenever genuine love is established, long-lasting togetherness could be planted. Such is what is revealed in the relationship between Amina and Ijeoma. She declares that:

"But we were in love, ... I craved Amina's presence for no other reason than to have it. It was certainly friendship too, this intimate companionship with someone who knew me in a way that no one else did: it was a heightened state of friendship. Maybe it was also a bit of infatuation. But what I knew for sure was that it was also love. Maybe love was some combination of friendship and infatuation. A deeply felt affection accompanied by a certain sort of awe. And by gratitude. And by a desire for a lifetime of togetherness. Pg 131.

Ijeoma, along the line, feels that maybe she is actually wrong, and she tries to purge herself from such guilt through personal prayer in the church. That fails to yield the expected result as captured in this statement by her.

Suddenly I felt an urge to pray. I wanted to ask for forgiveness for the things I had done in Nnewi. Not a day had passed when I did not remember those things. Not a day had passed when I did not crave those things, when I did not find myself wanting to repeat them. But now, I sat in church and for the first time I felt an overwhelming sense of guilt. I wanted to ask God to help me turn my thoughts away from Amina, to turn me instead onto the path of righteousness. I wanted to ask Him to guide me, to allow His word to echo in my heart. I opened my mouth to pray, but somehow the words of prayer

would not come. It was as if they had become stuck in my throat. I tried over and over again. Still no luck. After a while, I stood up and took myself back home. P 66

Due to family and societal pressure, Ijeoma is forced to a marriage with Chibundu, her childhood friend in primary school days. That marriage ended the relationship between Amina and Ijeoma. Amina is equally made to reason that marriage is between a man and a woman. The death of the relationship between Amina and Ijeoma gives birth to another episode of love relationship between Ijeoma and Ndidi. The relationship is ignited and blossomed into a mighty tree under the roof of Mama, Ijeoma's mother, yet she fails to realise that because she is occupied and blinded by religious and cultural beliefs to make sure that her only daughter marries a man. That is why immediately Chibundu comes around, she quickly links him up to her daughter which eventually leads to a forceful marriage that fails to stand the test of time at the end. Despite the marriage, Ijeoma continues her relationship with Ndidi, her female friend before marriage. She affirms to Ndidi that "he is my husband, yes, but you are the one I love." Pg 242

The marriage produces a girl child which opens another can of worms, the segregation and discrimination of females in the society. Chibundu expects a male child from Ijeoma, but he is disappointed to see a girl child at birth. He fails to shower sufficient love on both the child and the mother, that the girl grows up in that unhealthy marriage environment and equally realises that later in life. Ijeoma desires that her second pregnancy, which eventually ends in miscarriage, would be a boy so that she will be free from marriage which she describes as captivity. She says:

If he would only get his son, then maybe I would finally be excused from any more of those nighttime obligations. Maybe I could finally be released from this captivity of a marriage. If only the baby would come quickly, and not only come: if it would just be a boy. Please, Lord, I begged. P 264

Failure of Chibundu in proper upbringing of their child ignites and increases the love relationship between Ijeoma and Ndidi, which makes Ijeoma to confess openly that she loves Ndidi. Chibundu realises this later as he begs her to love him as well.

"I admit I was a little rough on you last night," he said. "We are husband and wife, and it shouldn't have to be that way." "Chibundu—" "I've been thinking, and my sense of it is that there's a way in which you can just tell yourself to love me instead of her. I shouldn't have to force myself on you night after night. I am your husband, and it shouldn't have to be that way." "Chibundu, that's not how it works." "How do you know if you don't try? You can just try. It shouldn't be that hard to love me. Or am I that unlovable?" "Chibundu, it's not that—" "Tell me, what exactly can she give you that you don't think I can?" Silence. Pg 247 We must understand that "Marriage is a promise, not just to marry, but also to love." Pg 248.

After Ijeoma's episode with Amina, she gets hooked up with Ndidi whom she lives with for over thirty years to the point of writing this piece after her heterosexual marriage with Chibundu collapses. Surprisingly, these homosexuals who are not allowed in the society meets secretly in a church building for the purpose of sisterhood identification.

“To the side of it, above a giant white cross, hung a sign that read FRIEND IN JESUS CHURCH OF GOD. Another sign, ... FOUNTAIN OF LOVE. “You brought me to church?” I whispered to Ndidi as we stood beneath the awning at the entrance, about to enter.” Pg 167

The author metaphorically posits here that church should not discriminate but open its doors to everyone who cares to listen and worship God because the qualification for making heaven is not a marriage certificate, for God is love.

Undue jungle justice the homosexuals face in the society is frowned at by the two selected authors. Chinelo Okparanta’s *Under the Udala Trees*, reveals an instance where “They stripped the lovers of their clothes and beat them all over until they were black and blue. They shouted “666” in their faces, and “God punish you!” P. 275. ‘666’ is a biblical number that is associated with the beast, the anti-Christ, and whosoever receives that mark is eternally doomed. The reference of this mark here shows that the homosexuals are likened to the anti-Christ and they are beasts which must be crushed by any means and the so called ‘innocent’ people have the right to put laws into their own hands by practicing jungle justice. This act is condemned by the author. Likewise, Chris Abani in *Graceland* portrays such terrible situation where some people, believed to be homosexuals, are indiscriminately punished.

“Hey, Elvis, are you homo? Release me small,” Redemption said. Elvis relaxed his grip. P. 181, ... Anybody who tries to defend the ‘homo’ will not go unpunished “Because dey will stone you too.” P. 213.

Ndidi paints such situation to Ijeoma on the danger the society places on their relationships. She says: “You’ll find out. But for now you’ll have to promise me that you won’t. You can’t let your mother know of it. No mentioning it to her. I can’t take you to it if you don’t promise.” “I wasn’t planning on mentioning it to Mama,” I said. “Good,” she replied. “Because mentioning it to anyone can cost some of us, if not all of us, our lives.” Pg 166

Chibundu, Ijeoma’s brief husband, highlights the purpose of religion as he compares church with business transactions. He posits that

“business is all about gathering as many customers as possible and retaining them. Religion is basically a business, a very large corporation. Take the Anglican or Catholic Church, for instance. You have all these doctrines that are set up, and we are told that God is the reason for all of them.” “Isn’t He?” I asked. Chibundu shook his head. “No. I don’t think He is.” “Why not?” “Because if you look deeply enough into those doctrines, you begin to see that the Church just wants to do whatever it can to get as many followers as possible and to keep them under control. This is the way business works. So the Catholic Church tells us that ‘Be fruitful and multiply’ means ‘Don’t use contraceptives.’ And people actually soak it up and wind up having twelve children that they can’t possibly take care of. And they continue to have more children for fear of using contraceptives and angering God. And really, it’s not even God who’s making them do it. It’s the Church that has interpreted God’s words to its own

benefit. Because the Church wants as many members as possible, as many followers as possible.” ... “My point is that business is the reason for things like doctrines. Business is the reason for words like ‘abomination.’ The Church is the oldest and most successful business known to man, because it knows not only how to recruit customers but also how to control them with things like doctrines and words like ‘abomination.’ Bottom line is, take your abomination with a grain of salt.” Pg 201

The authors reason that something is special about same sex marriage which humans might not ordinarily understand. Chibundu reveals to Ijeoma after he understands the makeup of his wife, how she is wired by her creator, in which none of them can do anything about it to resign to fate He concludes as their marriage ends that:

“I don’t hate you for it,” he said. “I really don’t. You know already that I don’t believe all that nonsense about abominations. Maybe there’s something special about that kind of love, about a man loving another man, or a woman loving another woman in that way. Maybe there’s something appealing about it.” P. 248. ... “But perhaps it didn’t matter, long or short, as long as we eventually found our way to where we needed to be” Pg 271.

We are, as proposed by the author, to find our ways to where we need to be. One belief should not dominate and crucify the other, but we should allow love and happiness to reign among us as we find eternal fulfilment in your choice.

Conclusion

The author concludes through the words of Ijeoma that marriage or relationship is like a bicycle with two wheels.

“And, of course, it does. Ndidi is one, and I am the other. We have now shared decades together, and though there can be no marriage between us (a relationship like ours is still too dangerous a thing, let alone a marriage), we feel ourselves every bit a couple We keep separate quarters, but we do spend many of our nights together. Pg 277 Bible establishes it in Hebrews 8: “God made a new covenant with the house of Israel, and with the house of Judah, not according to the covenant that He made with their fathers. If that first covenant had been faultless, then no place would have been made for the second. With that new covenant, He made the first old. And that first one was allowed to vanish away.” It is this verse that fills my mind these days. This, it seems to me, is the lesson of the Bible: this affirmation of the importance of reflection, and of revision, enough revision to do away with tired, old, even faulty laws. Sometimes I sit with my Bible in my hands, and I think to myself that God is nothing but an artist, and the world is His canvas. And I reason that if the Old and New Testaments are any indication, then change is in fact a major part of His aesthetic, a major part of His vision for the world. The Bible itself is an endorsement of change. Even biblical

covenants change: In the New Testament, no longer the need for animal sacrifices. Change. No longer the covenant of law, but rather the covenant of grace. Change. A focus on all mankind rather than a focus on the Jews. Change. So many other changes, if a person were the list-making type. Many days I reason to myself that change is the point of it all. And that everything we do should be a reflection of that vision of change. Maybe the rules of the Bible will always be in flux. Maybe God is still speaking and will continue to do so for always. Maybe He is still creating new covenants, only we were too deaf, too headstrong, too set in old ways to hear. Yes, there are the ways of God that have already been made known to us, but maybe there are also those ways in the process of being made known. Maybe we have only to open our ears and hearts and minds to hear. P 278-279.

As we conclude, we want to submit that hatred and unhealthy discrimination should not be encouraged in the society. Since God believes in change, then we should be more attentive to listen to Him and embrace positive changes. Religion and sexuality should not divide the people but everyone should be allowed to live with and practice what they believe in, just like the common slogan of “let the poor live”. Ijeome’s mother concludes that “All right,” she said. “All right ... God, who created you, must have known what He did. Enough is enough.” Pg 279. In summary, religion serves as a potent force in mapping territories and identities in Africa, intersecting with ethnicity, politics, culture, and social dynamics. Understanding these complexities is crucial for promoting peace, stability, and mutual respect among Africa's diverse religious communities.

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